

The Effect of Merit Awards on Physicians' Activity Rates in the English NHS

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: The economics literature on tournaments, contests, and prizes, has examined how the presence of future rewards, monetary or not, produces higher efforts on participants' effort to win the tournament. This literature particularly stresses the incentive effects of the rewards during the pre-tournament period. Yet less is known about the labour supply consequences of winning those tournaments. This paper studies the impact of winning a Clinical Excellence Award (CEA) on the inpatient activity rates of NHS physicians in the post-award period. The CEA financially reward NHS senior physicians who perform over and above the standard expected of their role. The scheme operates nationally as a rank-order tournament that is based on physicians' relative (clinical and non-clinical) performance. The value of individual awards ranges from £36,000 to £77,000 per annum across 4 levels – Bronze, Silver, Gold and Platinum –, which are paid in addition to physicians' basic salary. The awards are given for five years, after which physicians can apply for renewal or for higher-level awards.

Methods: We have assembled a rich dataset with physician-level panel information on NHS inpatient activity, CEA holders, and physician characteristics, for the years between 2008 and 2017. We measure inpatient activity as the annual count number of finished episodes of care, where a single episode is defined as a period of health care under one senior physician in one hospital provider. Adjusting for unobserved heterogeneity of physicians, we estimate a series of fixed-effects panel models that also include time trends and physicians' level of seniority.

Results: Our sample includes 1,346 CEA holders, who complete 6,791,885 episodes of care. We establish that there are significant increases in physicians' inpatient activity after winning Bronze and Silver CEA (more 85 and 120 episodes/year, respectively), but not after Gold and Platinum awards.